

Experiment Explanation

- ssh configuration for connection with the router and controller
 - **Connect the controller:** ssh one-to-rule-them-all
 - **Connect to the device from controller:** ssh device
- Here we have provided the public key of our system and that is added to the controller to access the controller via ssh

From the device we can switch the different forwarding techniques such as hardware offloading, software offloading and eBPF (TC) variant.

- Then, to measure the result,
 - **Connect the server:** exec itsys-d4-sink iperf3 -s
 - **Start tcpdump:** sudo ip netns exec itsys-d4-sink tcpdump -i ul-sink -w trace -s 250 <filename.pcap>
 - **Client send the server request:** sudo ip netns exec itsys-d4-source iperf3 -c 10.24.20.1

Above experiments take the records with 10 seconds and packet size is 250 bits.

- Plotting:
 - Collect the pcap file
 - Convert pcap to csv file (wireshark)
 - Remove unnecessary columns from csv (cut -d ',' -f 1,3,4,5,7,8 --complement filtered.csv > new_data.csv)
 - With the packet size and time we measure the results
 - All graphs are plot with excel tool